

**Ocean Cryosphere Exchanges in Antarctica:
Impacts on Climate and the Earth system**

Deployment of various moored instruments

Milestone MS2

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Milestone report

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1. Means of verification of the achievement of the milestone

Various instruments were deployed during two different campaigns to the continental slopes of the Weddell Sea and Dronning Maud Land (DML).

2. Work performed and main achievements

Two different field campaigns were used to deploy various instruments to generate data that would benefit collaborative analyses within the OCEAN:ICE community. These include primarily contributions from NPI and AWI. The deployment locations are displayed in Figure 1. Some of these instruments have been funded through OCEAN:ICE and others have been provided by other initiatives or projects.

Fig. 1: Deployment locations of moorings near the Fimbul Ice Shelf and in the eastern Weddell Sea are displayed with red stars. The underlying map is based on the International Bathymetric Chart of the Southern Ocean Version 2 (Dorschel et al., 2022)

2.1 Mooring deployments by NPI (Norwegian Polar Institute)

In January 2023, two Seabird bottom pressure recorders (in short BPR, SBE53) were deployed with oceanographic moorings at the continental slope near Fimbul Ice Shelf by NPI during their TrollTransect-cruise that utilizes the annual Troll station supply vessel cruises for oceanographic research and monitoring as part of the Troll Observing Network Multidisciplinary Ocean Moored Observatory (TONE-MOMO <https://www.npolar.no/en/tonel/>). Recovery will take place in January 2025. In addition, NPI will further contribute additional information on physical parameters (conductivity, temperature, depth, current velocities) from the Fimbul region based on sensors deployed within the same moorings. The measurements' purpose is to understand and monitor the Antarctic Slope Front dynamics and the access of Circumpolar Deep Water to the ice shelves in Dronning Maud Land.

2.2 Mooring deployments by AWI (Alfred Wegener Institute)

In April 2022, AWI had also deployed BPRs that compose part of an along-shelf network in combination with the NPI observations. The AWI moorings were deployed at the continental slope of the eastern Weddell Sea at 13°W (Hoppema, 2023), also to be recovered in early 2025 with the contribution of the OCEAN:ICE project. The expected data will be made available through the deliverable D1.6 and contribute to study the along-shelf connectivity between the Dronning Maud Land and the Weddell Sea. In addition, both NPI and AWI programmes will contribute additional information on physical parameters (e.g., conductivity, temperature, depth, current velocities) from these regions based on sensors that were deployed within the same moorings, to understand and monitor the frontal dynamics and warm water transport to the ice shelves in DML and the southern Weddell Sea.

2.3 References

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